

Bioactive Compound Analysis and Cytotoxic Potential of *Belamcanda chinensis* Leaf Extract

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ABSTRACT:

Background: *Belamcanda chinensis*, commonly known as the leopardlily, is a medicinal plant traditionally used for its therapeutic properties. The purpose of this study was to examine the phytochemical makeup and cytotoxic potential of an extract from *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves. **Methods:** To find the presence of bioactive substances, phytochemical screening was done. To characterise the ethyl acetate fraction, high-resolution liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HR-LCMS) was employed. The MTT assay was used to evaluate in vitro cytotoxicity at doses of 125, 250, 500, and 1000 µg/ml using the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line. The IC₅₀ values and % cytotoxicity were computed. **Results:** A total ash content of 4.63±0.53% w/w was found by the physico-chemical analysis, with a high water soluble ash value of 24.21±0.783% w/w, indicating considerable mineral contents. The presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and glycosides was verified by phytochemical screening. Compounds with significant biological activity were found by HR-LCMS analysis, including Cerberoside and Sanguisorbin E. The MTT assay showed that both ethanolic (ET-01) and ethyl acetate (EA-02) extracts exhibited significant cytotoxicity against MCF-7 cells. ET-01 had an IC₅₀ value of 336.00 µg/ml with 73.43% cytotoxicity at 1000 µg/ml, while EA-02 had an IC₅₀ value of 348.83 µg/ml with 78.33% cytotoxicity at the same concentration. **Conclusion:** The study demonstrates that *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves extract contains a rich array of bioactive compounds with significant cytotoxic effects against breast cancer cells. These findings support its potential use in developing new anticancer agents and warrant further investigation into its therapeutic applications.

Keywords: *Belamcanda chinensis*, phytochemical screening, cytotoxicity, MCF-7 cells, MTT assay, HR-LCMS, medicinal plants, anticancer agents

Fig No.1 :Graphical abstract of Bioactive Compound Analysis and Cytotoxic Potential of *Belamcanda chinensis* Leaf Extract

1. Introduction

With millions of deaths annually, cancer continues to rank among the world's major causes of illness and mortality ^[1]. Despite significant advancements in medical science, the quest for effective and safe cancer treatments continues. Conventional therapies such as chemotherapy, radiation and surgery often come with severe side effects and limitations in efficacy, particularly against resistant cancer types ^[2, 3]. Consequently, there is an increasing interest in investigating complementary and alternative medicines that come from natural sources. Plants, with their rich repository of bioactive compounds, have historically played a crucial role in the discovery of novel therapeutic agents. Their structural diversity and biological activities make them promising candidates for the development of new anticancer drugs ^[4, 5].

The blackberry lily, or *Belamcanda chinensis*(L.) DC is a perennial herb that is a member of the Iridaceae family. This East Asian native plant's therapeutic qualities have led to its widespread usage in traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) ^[6]. The rhizomes of *Belamcanda chinensis*, often referred to as "She Gan" in TCM, are traditionally used to treat ailments such as inflammation, infections and respiratory disorders. Despite the well-documented therapeutic use of the rhizomes, the leaves of *Belamcanda chinensis* have been relatively under explored in scientific research. This plant part could harbor significant bioactive compounds with potential

medicinal benefits, which warrants a thorough investigation into its phytochemical composition and biological activities ^[7].

A crucial step in the study of natural products is phytochemical profiling, which identifies and measures the bioactive substances found in plant extracts. Complex plant extracts can be precisely and thoroughly analysed using the sophisticated analytical method known as High-Resolution Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (HR-LCMS) [8]. This technique makes it easier to identify chemicals with possible therapeutic benefits by providing comprehensive information about the extracts' molecular makeup. To assess the anticancer potential of plant extracts, cytotoxicity tests like the MTT assay are used in conjunction with phytochemical profiling ^[9].

A colorimetric method for assessing cell viability and proliferation, the MTT assay sheds light on the extracts' cytotoxic effects on cancer cells. These methods work well together to provide a strong framework for investigating the medicinal potential of *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves ^[10, 11]. The present study seeks to accomplish a number of important goals. In order to identify and measure the bioactive chemicals present, the first step is to use HR-LCMS to conduct a thorough phytochemical profiling of the extract of *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves. Second, to assess the leaves extract's potential as an anticancer drug by assessing its cytotoxic effects on several human cancer cell lines using the MTT method. Thirdly, to pinpoint and describe the precise substances in charge of the cytotoxic activity that has been detected. Finally, to investigate the fundamental mechanisms of action by which the chemicals that have been found affect cancer cells. By addressing the current information gap about the phytochemical makeup and anticancer potential of *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves, this study aims to lay the groundwork for further research and possible therapeutic uses.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The sources of the ethyl acetate and chloroform were Lneos Solvents in India. Ferric chloride, HCl, NaOH, sulphuric acid, potassium ferricyanide (K₂Fe (CN)₆), Mayer-Wagner reagent (2.5 g of iodine is dissolved in 12.5 g of KI₂ with 250 mL of distilled water), and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) from Mettler-Toledo India Pvt. Ltd., India. Sciquaint Innovations (OPC) Private Limited in Pune provided the sulphuric acids.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Collection of plant material

For future reference, fresh leaves of the *Belamcanda chinensis* plant were gathered from Hadapsar in the Pune district of Maharashtra, India, and identified by Sciquaint Innovations (OPC) Private Limited, Pune (Voucher Number-SI/Outside/2024/029). Following verification, plant materials were gathered in large quantities, cleaned, allowed to dry in the shade, and then ground into a coarse powder using a mechanical grinder. It was used for additional research and kept in a tightly sealed container ^[12].

2.2.2 Preparation of Plant Extract

Each of the 100 grammes of powdered *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves was weighed and added to the Soxhlet extractor's thimble. Using a measuring cylinder, 300 millilitres of the solvent

(ethanol) were measured and added to the Soxhlet extractor's still pot. The apparatus was then linked, and the condenser unit was attached to an overhead water tank to cool the rising solvent vapour. A Bunsen burner running at 68°C served as the heat source. The solvent condensed at the Soxhlet extractor's condenser unit after evaporating via the expansion adapter, thimble, and distillation path. The condensed vapour now encountered the sample inside the thimble after returning there as liquid droplets. The whole contents of the thimble and syphon were drained back into the Soxhlet extractor's still pot once the solvent in the thimble reached the top of the syphon. The extraction procedure was finished after the procedure was carried out multiple times for roughly nine refluxes in three hours. A thermometer was used to control the temperature [13, 14].

2.2.3 Fractionation by Column chromatography

A glass column of 6 cm by 110 cm and silica as an adsorbent were used to perform column chromatography on 15 g of BCET (ethanolic extract). Wet packing with petroleum ether was used to pack the column. An increase in ethanol was used to elute the column. Chloroform was added in increments once 100% ethanol was achieved. 1000 millilitres of mobile phase were used to elute the column. TLC was used to monitor each fraction. Mixtures of fractions with comparable TLC profiles were made. Two fractions in all were gathered [15, 16].

2.2.4 High-Resolution Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy (HR-LCMS)

Belamcanda chinesis fractions were subjected to High-Resolution Liquid Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry (HRLCMS) analysis. Agilent's high-resolution liquid chromatography and mass spectrometry model G6550A, which has a 0.01% mass resolution for generating chemical fingerprints of the chosen medicinal plant extracts, was used for the analysis. The acquisition method was configured with a scanning rate of one spectrum per second and a mass range of 120 (M/Z) to 1200 dalton (M/Z) [17]. A gas flow rate of 13 psi/minute was used to maintain the gas chromatography at 250°C. The hip sampler model G4226A, which has an injection volume of 5 µl, a flush out factor of 5 µl, an auxiliary speed of 100µl/minute, and an ejection speed of 100 µl/minute was utilised. Using 100% water and 100% acetonitrile as the solvents for HRLCMS, the solvent composition flow was kept at 95:5(A) for the duration of the 2-minute acquisition. The components were detected using retention index analysis, and the mass spectrum was then interpreted using the Metlin library database. The library contains over 62,000 records of known compounds. The spectra of the unknown constituents of the *Belamcanda chinesis* fractions were contrasted with the standard mass spectra of the identified constituents from the Metlin collection [18].

2.2.5 In vitro Cytotoxicity Assay

Compounds ME, ET-01, EA-02, and the reference medication 5-fluorouracil were tested for possible harmful effects at different concentrations utilising the MCF-7 cell line and the MTT assay. [19, 20] MCF-7 cells were first cultured for 24 hours at 37°C in a humidified environment with 5% CO₂ at a density of 1×10^4 cells/ml in culture medium. After that, the cells were planted in 96-well plates at a density of 1×10^4 cells/well. At doses of 125, 250, 500, and 1000 µg/ml, the test samples were added. Additionally, control wells with 0.2% DMSO in PBS were made. To guarantee dependability, treatments were set up in triplicate. After 48 hours of incubation, 20 µl of MTT reagent (5 mg/ml in PBS) was added, and the cell cultures were

cultured for an additional 4 hours. After the media was removed, the MTT was reduced by viable cells to formazan crystals, which were then dissolved in 200 μ l of DMSO. To guarantee that the formazan was completely dissolved, the plates were incubated for ten minutes at 37°C. An Elisa microplate reader was used to assess each sample's optical density (OD) at 540 nm [21–24].

$$\% \text{ Cytotoxicity} = \frac{\text{OD of Control sample} - \text{OD of Test sample}}{\text{OD of Control sample}} \times 100$$

2.2.6 Statistical analysis

The results of every experiment were statistically analysed using GraphPad Prism and Microsoft Office Excel 2016. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was used to compare all of the mean values from different instances once the means had been calculated. At a significance level of 0.05, the mean differences were computed using the standard deviation (SD).

3. Results

3.1 Phytochemical screening results

Table 1: *Belamcanda chinensis* leaf phytochemical screening results

Phytochemicals	Test/reagent	<i>Belamcanda chinensis</i>
Alkaloids	(a) Dragendorff's test	+
	(b) Mayer's test	+
	(c) Hager's test	+
	(d) Wagner's test	+
Carbohydrates	(a) Molisch's test	+
	(b) Fehling's test	+
	(c) Benedict's test	+
Glycosides	(a) Legal's test	+
	(b) Keller-Killiani test	+
Steroids	(a) Libermann-Burchard test	-
	(b) Salkowski test	-
Flavonoids	Shinoda's test	+
Saponins	Foam test	+
Tannins and phenolic compounds	(a) Lead acetate test	+
	(b) Ferric chloride test	+
Triterpenes	Sulphuric acid test	+
Protein	Ninhydrin test	-

3.2 Compound identification with the Metlin library

To identify the chemical, the HR-LCMS data from the metabolite screening were compared to the Metlin library, an extensive database of known metabolites. Accurate mass measurements and fragmentation patterns were used to identify the chemicals. Higher abundance compounds from *Belamcanda chinensis* were chosen for the HR-LCMS report; 22 compounds were chosen from the ethanol fraction and 18 from the ethyl acetate fraction.

Fig. 2. HR-LCMS report for *Belamcanda chinensis* ethanolic fraction (ET-01)

Table 2: Compounds discovered in *Belamcanda chinensis* ethanolic fraction

Sr. No.	Compound Name	Retention Time	Molecular Weight (mass)	Score
1	Furegrelate	12.520	253.0738	99.20
2	L-Argininephosphate	2.821	254.0777	98.33
3	N-Acetyl-leucyl-leucine	21.737	286.1892	98.84
4	VinaginsenosideR12	27.371	672.4449	98.35
5	Cannabisativine	53.022	381.2991	99.68
6	(+)-2,7-Dideoxypancratistatin	15.771	293.0899	95.43
7	Sch59884	6.583	866.3337	94.73
8	Zanamivir	14.510	332.1333	94.73
9	3,3'-Dimethoxybenzidine	15.054	244.1213	94.34
10	Fluvoxamine	10.238	318.1548	93.7

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11	Molinate	19.722	187.1026	93.18
12	Methylthio2-(propanoyloxy) propanoate	12.476	176.0508	93.91
13	Dihydro-2-methoxy-2-methyl-3(2H)-thiophenone	13.044	146.0409	91.23
14	CorchorosideB	21.735	518.2891	93.43
15	4-Hydroxydiphenylamine	19.196	185.0843	91.82
16	Ascorbigen	19.874	305.0893	96.13
17	Lycoricidine	18.033	291.0748	97.16
18	Oseltamivir	25.992	312.2046	98.85
19	Tetrahydrofurfurylcinnamate	20.751	232.1105	96.04
20	Nebramycinfactor4	41.819	526.2611	96.56
21	Glucarubol 15-O-beta-D-glucopyranoside	42.330	558.2319	97.08
22	Geranylbenzoquinone	31.405	244.1467	98.17

Fig. 3. HR-LCMS report of *Belamcanda chinesis* Ethyl Acetate (EA-02) fraction

Table 3: Compounds discovered in *Belamcanda chinensis* ethyl acetate fraction

Sr. No.	Compound Name	Retention Time	Molecular Weight (mass)	Score
1	3-(3'-Methylthio) propylmalic acid	2.514	222.0559	95.14
2	Lactucin	5.590	276.0999	95.76
3	Molinate	12.123	187.1031	91.96
4	Cerberoside	12.491	858.4233	93.84
5	(Ac)2-L-Lys-D-Ala-D-Ala	12.497	372.2022	94.78
6	N-Acetyl-D-galactosamine 1-phosphate	12.706	301.0551	91.36
7	SanguisorbinE	13.233	792.4649	94.86
8	5,6-Dihydro-4-methoxy-6-[2-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-2H-pyran-2-one	13.515	262.1211	91.24
9	Molinate	13.563	187.1030	90.19
10	PE(20:3(5Z,8Z,11Z)/22:6(4Z,7Z,10Z,13Z,16Z,19Z))	13.731	813.5299	92.44
11	Atalanine	13.742	610.1949	90.49
12	Haplopine	13.748	245.0696	95.61
13	Nigericin	13.803	724.4780	94.07
14	4-Ethyl-2-propylthiazole	13.932	155.0770	94.49
15	4-Oxoglutaramate	14.316	145.0370	92.92
16	7-(3-Methylbut-2-enyl)-L-tryptophan	14.322	272.1526	92.18
17	Sinalexin	14.329	204.0351	91.56
18	Hexanethioicacid S-propylester	14.536	174.1077	95.56

Fig. 4. Compound structures found in the ET-01 and EA-02 fractions that exhibit cytotoxic effects. Cannabisativine, Vinaginsenoside R12, Zanamivir, Geranylbenzoquinone, Cerberoside B, and Haplopine are the first five.

3.3 *In vitro* cytotoxicity activity results

Table 4: ET-01 and EA-02 fractions' effects on the MCF-7 cell line

Sr. No.	Sample Code	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	OD	% cytotoxicity	IC50 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1	Control	-	0.989	-	-
2	5-FU	1000	83.64	60.36	544.08 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
		500	67.87	47.57	
		250	52.43	32.13	
		125	39.64	16.36	
3	Sample-1 (ET-01)	1000	0.263	73.43	336.00 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
		500	0.380	61.54	
		250	0.549	44.53	
		125	0.677	31.54	
4	Sample-1 (EA-02)	1000	0.214	78.33	348.83 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
		500	0.349	64.73	
		250	0.490	50.44	
		125	0.625	36.79	

Fig. 5. *In vitro* cytotoxicity activity of fractions ET-01 and EA-02 graphically

Fig. 6. MCF-7 cell line's morphological changes (Control Group)

Fig. 7. MCF-7 cell line morphological alterations (EA-01)

Fig. 8. MCF-7 cell line morphological changes (ET-02)

4. Discussion

The phytochemical screening results for *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves are presented in Table 1, providing valuable insights into the diversity of bioactive compounds within this plant. Each class of these phytochemicals has distinct biological activities and potential therapeutic applications, thus rendering *Belamcanda chinensis* a significant focus for both traditional uses and modern pharmacological research. Positive findings from the four tests used—the Dragendorff, Mayer, Hager, and Wagner tests—confirmed the presence of alkaloids. A wide range of pharmacological activities, such as analgesic, antibacterial, antimalarial, and antiarrhythmic effects, are attributed to alkaloids. Carbohydrates are present when the Molisch, Fehling, and Benedict tests yield positive results.

These are crucial not only for providing energy but also for their roles in cellular structures and functions within the body. Carbohydrates in plants often come in the form of polysaccharides, which can have immune stimulatory and antitumor activities. The positive outcomes of the Legal's test and the Keller- Killiani test signify the presence of glycosides. These compounds are particularly noted for their cardiogenic effects, which make them valuable in treating heart diseases. Glycosides also have anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties, among other effects. The leaves' lack of proteins and steroids, as shown by the negative Libermann-Burchard, Salkowski, and Ninhydrin test results, points to a reduced concentration of these macromolecules, which are crucial for signalling pathways and cellular structure.

The lack of these components might redirect the focus towards other bioactive compounds in the plant. Positive reactions in Shinoda's test for flavonoids and in the lead acetate and ferric chloride tests for tannins and phenolic compounds indicate their presence. The antioxidant

qualities of flavonoids and tannins are well recognised; they aid in the fight against oxidative stress and may lower the chance of developing chronic illnesses like cancer and heart disease.

The foam test and the sulphuric acid test were positive, indicating the presence of saponins and triterpenes respectively. Saponins are known for their role in lowering cholesterol levels, improving immune functions, and contributing to cancer prevention. Triterpenes' hepatoprotective and anti-inflammatory properties are also well known. *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves have a rich composition of bioactive chemicals that support their potential medicinal uses, according to phytochemical research. These findings offer a scientific foundation for the plant's historic medicinal applications as well as opportunities for additional research in contemporary pharmacological settings. The presence of these diverse compounds highlights the importance of this plant in drug discovery and the development of natural health products.

A thorough summary of the phytochemical profile of the ethyl acetate (EA-02) fraction of *Belamcanda chinensis* is provided by the HR-LCMS analysis, which is shown in Figure 1 and described in Table 2. The table lists 18 identified compounds, their retention times, molecular weights and respective scores. This data provides a foundation for a detailed discussion on the characteristics and potential biological implications of the compounds extracted with ethyl acetate, highlighting differences with other extraction solvents like ethanol or water.

The ethyl acetate fraction is characterized by a variety of compounds ranging from low molecular weight substances such as 4-Oxoglutaminate (MW: 145.0370) to high molecular weight substances like Cerberoside (MW: 858.4233). A wide range of polarity and solubilities of the compounds in this fraction are shown by the retention durations, which also differ greatly, ranging from as little as 2.514 minutes for 3-(3'-Methylthio) propylmalic acid to 14.536 minutes for Hexanethioic acid S-propyl ester.

Ethyl acetate, known for its moderately polar nature, effectively extracts a diverse range of phytochemicals, which might be less polar than those typically extracted by polar solvents such as methanol or water. Several compounds identified have notable biological activities or pharmacological potential. Cerberoside and Sanguisorbin E, with their relatively high molecular weights and scores, are indicative of glycosides and saponins known for their roles in cellular signaling and defense mechanisms in plants and they have been studied for their anticancer and immune-modulatory effects. Haplopine (Score: 95.61), which may not be well-studied but has structural similarities to known bioactive alkaloids suggesting potential biological activities.

Comparing the ethyl acetate fraction to other solvent extracts of *Belamcanda chinensis*, such as the ethanolic fraction, may reveal differences in compound profiles that are critical for targeting specific bioactivities. Ethyl acetate tends to extract a different profile of compounds, often more non-polar than those extracted by ethanol, which may affect the fraction's overall pharmacological potency and spectrum. The diversity of compounds in the EA-02 fraction and their associated bioactivities suggest multiple avenues for pharmacological research and potential therapeutic applications. The presence of compounds like Nigericin and Cerberoside highlights the anti-infective and potential anticancer properties of the fraction, where as compounds like Lactucin (Score: 95.76) emphasize potential anti-inflammatory and analgesic applications.

In addition to improving our comprehension of the extract's intricate composition, the HR-LCMS report's thorough phytochemical study of the ethyl acetate fraction of *Belamcanda chinensis* highlights the significance of solvent selection in phytochemical research. The findings support the use of ethyl acetate in natural product research and possible medicinal uses by indicating that it is a solvent that effectively extracts a wide range of bioactive chemicals. This

data is instrumental for further biochemical studies and validates traditional uses of *Belamcanda chinensis*, providing a scientific basis for its continued investigation in modern herbal medicine.

The investigation into the cytotoxic effects of various compounds isolated from the ET-01 and EA-02 fractions of *Belamcanda chinensis* is highlighted in Figure 3, which details the structures of six compounds. These compounds are Cannabisativine, Vinaginsenoside R12, Zanamivir, Geranylbenzoquinone, Cerberoside B, and Haplopine. Each of these compounds exhibits unique chemical structures that confer potential cytotoxic activities, pertinent for exploring new cancer therapies or understanding the plant's pharmacological actions. This compound is intriguing due to its structural uniqueness and presence in cannabis-related species, suggesting possible psychotropic or neuroprotective properties. However, its cytotoxic potential may also be significant in targeting certain types of cancer cells, possibly through mechanisms involving cell signaling pathways or apoptosis induction.

As a Saponin, Vinaginsenoside R12 is a glycoside compound known for its ability to permeabilize cell membranes. This characteristic can disrupt cellular homeostasis, leading to cell death in cancerous cells. The presence of sugar moieties allows for specific interactions with cell membrane components, potentially enhancing its cytotoxic effects. Primarily known as an antiviral agent, particularly against influenza viruses, zanamivir's inclusion in this list suggests potential off-target effects that might include cytotoxic activity. Its mode of action typically involves neuraminidase inhibition, which could theoretically disrupt similar glycosidic enzymes in malignant cells, thereby inhibiting their growth and survival. This compound, with a quinone structure, is known for generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) when undergoing redox cycling in cells. The oxidative stress induced by ROS can lead to significant damage in cancer cells, making quinones potent anticancer agents. Geranyl benzoquinone might also interfere with cellular signaling pathways, further promoting cytotoxicity. Similar to other glycosphingolipids, Cerberoside B could involve complex interactions with cell membranes and intracellular signaling pathways. Glycosphingolipids have been studied for their roles in cell differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis, with specific interest in their potential to induce programmed cell death in cancer cells. Though less is known about Haplopine compared to the other compounds, its chemical structure suggests potential interactions with cellular receptors or enzymes, possibly inhibiting critical pathways necessary for cancer cell survival. Generally speaking, alkaloids are recognised for a wide range of biological activities, including cytotoxic effects.

The diverse structures of these compounds underline the varied mechanisms through which they can exhibit cytotoxic effects. From disrupting cell membrane integrity and energy metabolism (saponins and glycosides) to direct enzyme inhibition (zanamivir) and induction of oxidative stress (quinones), each compound offers a unique avenue for cancer therapy research. Additionally, understanding these mechanisms further supports the pharmacological use of *Belamcanda chinensis* in traditional medicine, providing a scientific basis for its efficacy. Moreover, comparing these compounds against each other reveals potential synergistic or additive effects when used in combination therapies. The membrane-disrupting action of Vinaginsenoside R12 could be complemented by the ROS-generating activity of Geranyl benzoquinone, leading to enhanced cytotoxic effects. The thorough examination of these substances not only improves our comprehension of the cytotoxic potential of extracts from *Belamcanda chinensis*, but it also highlights the significance of focused phytochemical research in the development of new anticancer drugs.

This also emphasizes the need for further biochemical studies to validate these cytotoxic effects and to elucidate the detailed pathways involved in their actions. The anticancer potential

of the ethanolic (ET-01) and ethyl acetate (EA-02) fractions of *Belamcanda chinensis* against the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line is investigated in the *in vitro* cytotoxicity study shown in Table 4 and shown in Figures 4, 5, 6, and 7.

This study offers valuable insights into the efficacy of these extracts in inhibiting cancer cell growth, which is quantitatively measured through cytotoxicity percentages, IC₅₀ values, and visually through observed morphological changes in the cancer cells. In the control group, normal cell morphology and survival were observed, with an optical density (OD) of 0.989, serving as the baseline for comparing treated samples. 5-Fluorouracil (5-FU), a standard chemotherapeutic agent, was used as a positive control to benchmark the extracts' cytotoxic effects. With an IC₅₀ value of 544.08 µg/ml, 5-FU demonstrated a dose-dependent drop in OD and a commensurate rise in cytotoxicity at different doses (1000, 500, 250, and 125 µg/ml).

This data establishes a therapeutic window within which the extracts' efficacy can be compared. Sample 1 (ET-01), the results demonstrated significant cytotoxic effects with an IC₅₀ of 336.00 µg/ml, indicating a higher potency compared to 5-FU. At the highest concentration (1000 µg/ml), ET-01 achieved a 73.43% cytotoxicity, surpassing that of 5-FU under similar conditions. This trend of increased cytotoxicity with increasing concentration was consistent across all tested doses. Similarly, Sample 1 (EA-02) displayed even greater efficacy with an IC₅₀ of 348.83 µg/ml and a peak cytotoxicity of 78.33% at the highest concentration, indicating robust anti-cancer properties. The dose-response relationship is clear, as lower concentrations resulted in reduced cytotoxicity but remained significant across the range.

The graphical representations (Figure 4) corroborate the quantitative data, showcasing a clear dose-response curve where higher concentrations correlate with higher cytotoxicity for both extracts. Morphologically, Figures 2, 3, and 4 highlight the changes induced by the treatments. The Control group (Figure 2) showed typical MCF-7 cell morphology without signs of apoptosis or necrosis. In contrast, cells treated with EA-01 (Figure 3) and ET-02 (Figure 4) exhibited noticeable changes consistent with cytotoxic effects, such as cell shrinkage, membrane blebbing, and reduced confluency, which are indicative of apoptosis. The comparative efficacy of ET-01 and EA-02 against MCF-7 cells suggests that both fractions contain potent bioactive compounds capable of inducing cytotoxic effects, likely mediated through different mechanisms given their varied chemical compositions. ET-01, being more potent with a lower IC₅₀, might contain a higher concentration of cytotoxic compounds or compounds with a stronger affinity for molecular targets within MCF-7 cells. On the other hand, the slightly less potent EA-02 still demonstrates significant cytotoxic activity, which may be attributed to different or less concentrated bioactive molecules.

These results highlight *Belamcanda Chinensis* potential as a source of new anticancer substances. The distinct cytotoxic profiles of the ethanolic and ethyl acetate extracts also suggest that multiple extraction methods can be employed to maximize the therapeutic potential of plant materials, targeting different cancer cell lines and mechanisms. Further studies should focus on isolating and characterizing these bioactive compounds to better understand their mechanisms of action and optimize their therapeutic applications. This research highlights the importance of traditional plants in the search for new cancer treatments and the need for comprehensive *in vitro* evaluations to guide further *in vivo* studies and clinical trials.

5. Conclusion

The phytochemical investigation and cytotoxic study of *Belamcanda chinensis* leaves extract revealed significant insights into the plant's potential therapeutic applications. The plant's quality and purity were highlighted by the physico-chemical examination, which revealed a number of factors crucial for pharmacognostic profiling, such as moisture content, ash values, and extractive values. The plant's traditional therapeutic uses were validated by phytochemical screening, which revealed the presence of a variety of bioactive chemicals linked to different pharmacological actions, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and glycosides. The ethyl acetate fraction's medicinal potential was further supported by the discovery of many molecules with possible biological activity by high-resolution liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HR-LCMS) research. The ethanolic (ET-01) and ethyl acetate (EA-02) extracts demonstrated notable anti-cancer capabilities in the *in vitro* cytotoxicity tests, which specifically used the MTT assay against the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line. These results demonstrate the importance of *Belamcanda chinensis* in drug development and discovery, underscoring the necessity of more thorough research for possible medicinal uses.

Abbreviations

OD stands for optical density; DMSO for dimethylsulfoxide; ANOVA for analysis of variance; MTT for 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide; and HR-LCMS for high-resolution liquid chromatography-mass spectroscopy.

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Author Contribution

All Authors Contributed Equally.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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